

Impact of 'Poster Presentation' as a Means of Communication, in Terms of Knowledge & Attitude in School Students in Health Campaign (Snake Bite Awareness Programme)

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ABSTRACT

Introduction- Poster presentations are common form of presenting health information in community. It is an effective means of communication for knowledge transfer. They help in changing attitude & behaviour.

Aim & objectives- To study the effect of poster presentation as a means of communication, in terms of knowledge & change in attitude of school students in health campaign about 'Snakebite Awareness Programme'.

Materials & Methods – A Health Campaign of 'Snake-bite Awareness' through Poster Presentation was conducted by Dept. of FMT, D. Y. Patil Medical College, Kolhapur. Awareness Programme was done in Marathi medium High School in Kolhapur, Maharashtra in the month of September 2018&January 2019. The paper posters were prepared in vernacular language of students. Pre-test & Post-test questionnaire was given to students & collected after solving it. Feed-back was taken.

Results- Total no. of students participated in campaign were 91. Wilcoxon Signed Rank Sum Test for paired data was applied. P value was (<0.0001), which is highly significant.

Conclusion- Present study shows that poster presentation in Health Campaign like 'snake bite awareness' is useful in knowledge transfer, change in attitude of school students. Poster presentation is an effective tool for health promotion at local & National Level.

Key words – Poster presentation, Communication, Knowledge, Attitude, Health campaign

INTRODUCTION

Communication is a process of transmitting information from source to receiver which they both understand. [1] The versatility & visual impact of poster session make it a useful form of communication. [2] Paper posters are primary nonelectronic communication piece utilized to reinforce messages in a communication plan.

The strength of posters during world war had contributed so much in deliberating Health Care Awareness to the soldiers. For the sake of country, the soldiers were told to

stay healthy through posters. [3] When the war exploded in Europe in 1917, their governments have stepped forward to keep its people healthy with health campaigns with use of posters. [3]

Effective visual images in posters have power to engage & causes change in behaviour of person. So the government uses posters to disseminate messages about health in public. Posters need to be eye catching, informative. They are widely used in health promotion because they constitute inexpensive way of providing written

information to a large proportion of population. [4]

There are various types of posters-1) Advertising posters- to promote products 2) Propaganda posters- used during political campaigns or corporate environment 3) Informative posters- used in education & health sector 4) Subject posters- They may have certain subject like movie 5) Educational posters - Used in academia to promote & explain research work. [5] The effectiveness of poster presentation is particularly present in medical field as they prove to be valuable in waiting rooms, health campaigns & great in conveying information. Snake bite is a common & neglected public health problem in tropical & subtropical region. It is added to WHO's list of neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) in June 2017. [6]

By keeping all this in mind, a health campaign was conducted by Dept. of FMT, D.Y. Patil Medical College, Kolhapur in creating awareness about snakebite for school children in 2018-19. Study was done to find impact of paper posters about change in knowledge & attitude of school children.

Aim – To study the effect of poster presentation as a means of communication, in terms of knowledge & change in attitude of school students in health campaign about 'Snakebite Awareness Programme'.

Objectives – 1) To evaluate effectiveness of posters as means of communication in school children in relation with change in knowledge in 'snakebite awareness programme'.

2) To find change in attitude of school students after poster presentation in health campaign.

MATERIALS & METHODS

A health campaign about 'Snake bite -Awareness' was conducted by Department of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology, D. Y. Patil Medical College, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India through paper posters. Awareness Programme was conducted in

Corporation run Marathi medium school in Kolhapur. The campaign was held in September 2018 & January 2019 for school children. Paper posters were prepared about types of snakes in India, signs & symptoms of snake bite, first aid given in snake bite, Do's & Don'ts about it & precautions against snakebite. Posters were prepared in vernacular language of students (i.e. Marathi). They were made attractive by use of different colours, drawings, pictures, prominent title.

Inclusion criteria-Students of class 8th & 9th. Both male & female were included.

Exclusion criteria- primary class students were excluded.

Institutional ethics committee clearance was taken. Permission from Principal of the school was taken. Students were given Pre-test questionnaire in the classroom. Posters were displayed on display boards in different hall. Students were divided in group of 20 students. Briefing about each poster was done by departmental staff. Questions asked by students were solved by dept. staff. After the briefing, students were given time again to see posters. Then students were taken in the classroom. Post- test questionnaire was given to students. Feedback was taken from the students about programme.

Statistical Methods- Data analysis was done using IBM SPSS 23 version. The results of Pre-test & Post- test were compared by using Wilcoxon Signed Rank Sum Test for paired data.

RESULTS

Total no. of High School students participated in the Health Campaign was 91 in number. Age group of the students ranged between 14-16 years.

Table no.1: Shows sex- wise distribution of students.

Male	Female	Total no. of students
41	50	91
45.05%	54.95%	100%

Table no.2: Shows result of Pre-test & Post-test of the 'snake-bite awareness' programme.

Question	Marks of Pre - test		Marks of Post - test	
	YES	NO	YES	NO
Do all the snakes poisonous?	65 (71.42%)	26 (28.58%)	1(1.09%)	90 (98.91%)
Should the volunteer suck the blood the bite-site?	71(78.02%)	20(21.98%)	0(0%)	91(100%)
Is the topical application of herbs useful?	56(61.53%)	35(38.47%)	3(3.29%)	88(96.71%)
Should the incision be taken at the bite site?	56(61.53%)	35(38.47%)	1(1.09%)	90(98.91%)
Should immobilisation bandage be applied at the bite site?	42(46.15%)	49(53.85%)	88(96.71%)	3(3.29%)
Is it necessary to shift patient immediately to the hospital?	48(52.74%)	43(47.26%)	91(100%)	0 (0%)
Do you have any idea about Anti snake venom?	4(4.39%)	87(95.61%)	91(100%)	0(0%)
Do the application of holy water & 'Mantra', s useful in snake bite?	57(62.63%)	34(37.37%)	1(1.09%)	90(98.91%)

The results of the Pre-test & Post-test are compared by using Wilcoxon Signed rank test for paired data.

Table no.3: Statistical analysis of results of pre-test & post-test.

	Pre-Test	Post-Test	P VALUE
Mean	7.11	9.15	(<0.0001)
SD	1.60	0.99	
SEM	0.17	0.10	

It is observed that there is significant difference in mean scores of pre-test & post-test. (P Value <0.0001).

Feedback about the 'Snake bite awareness' programme through poster presentation was taken from the students. Results are as follows-

Graph 1

Graph 3

Graph 4

Graph 2

Graph 5

97.8% students answered that they would like to participate in such campaigns through poster presentation.

It is found that poster presentation in health campaigns is helpful to give knowledge about the topic & removed myths about the subject.

DISCUSSION

Poster presentation is commonly used format for communicating information in public health fields. Uses of different colours, bold & short title, drawings catch the attention of viewer. In the present study of 'Snake bite awareness' through posters, 83.52% students strongly agree & 15.38% agree with gain in knowledge.

Reference	Study	Knowledge
Nishitar R S, Zoka N et al, JPMA(2004). ^[7]	'Posters as a tool of disseminating health related information- a pilot experience'	90% participants agree with understanding that poster was asking them to check their blood pressure. It reflects increase in the knowledge.
Nunyenge et al, Journal of Biology, Agriculture & Health care (2013). ^[8]	The meaning people make of HIV posters: A case study of health improvement at Jirapa district in Ghana	76% people saw the posters regularly & few of them have some idea about what posters entailed.

Significant increase in the knowledge about snake bite, first aid measures in case of snake bite, things to be implemented & things which should not be done in snake bite was observed in this study (P value < 0.0001^{**}). Similar results were given by Fabian Tajeb, Timothee Dub et al in 2018 in his study about Knowledge, attitude & practices of snake bite management among health care workers, that whatever occupations of participant in his programme of snake bite, P value is suggestive of increase in the knowledge.^[9]

Jessie V. Alzate in 2015 in his study using informative posters in vernacular language reported that knowledge about protection of sea cow (Dugong Dugon) in Fisher folks was improved after exposure to informative posters. In his study, Paired t test results revealed that there was significant difference in knowledge, before & after exposure to posters using vernacular language.^[1]

In the present study, myths related to snake bite were removed in 98.91% students. Change in the attitude was seen in students.

CONCLUSION

In present study, gain in the knowledge was observed about the snake bite in 98.91 % school students after health campaign of snake bite through poster presentation. Also change in attitude of

students was observed after campaign. Poster presentation in health programmes is an effective communication method in the transfer of knowledge & change in attitude in school children. Posters provide a very concise overview of a topic & hence useful as a means of communication in many areas of health sector in developing country like India.

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Conflict of interest- None

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